

THE COMMUNICATIVE PURPOSE OF EQUIVALENCE IN TRANSLATION
MEANS OF EXPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Equivalence degrees, place of degrees at uprising the equivalence, method of application are considered relevant issues in the translation. The aim is to identify the problems of the issues raised by equivalence, determine the value of equivalence, comparing similarity of meanings between the original text and translation. Objectives: To determine the degree of equivalence in translation, to study phrases while maintaining the goal of communication, determining equivalent meaning in comparisons and special words. The object of our research is the form of comparisons and phrases of the original text converted to text of translation; and the equivalent forms in the translated text is the subject of research. The study used the method of comparative analysis. The first study of equivalence in translation of literary texts in the Uzbek translation is the actuality of the study. Study materials can be used in teaching of "Theory and Practice of Translation" and "linguistics culture". Scientific research work consists of an introduction, conclusion and bibliography. At transition of equivalent phrases of original texts and translation observed constriction of their meaning, as well as at the transition from the original text to text of translation, there is reductions of their meaning and reception, as a supplement, the new value.

Keywords: Equivalence, adequacy, reference, communication, denotative, expressive, metalinguistic function.

INTRODUCTION

The most important factor of culture that connects different nations is translation studies. Translation is the most important aspect of inter-national communication, through translation the works of scholars and poets are translated into different languages, and ties between peoples are connected to each other. The most laborious type of translation for any language is the translation by finding the equivalent version.

The translated text is equal to the original text and should create an impression of unity with it. Accordingly, one of the tasks of the translation is that the translated text takes the full communicative place of the original and presents a harmonious balance of artistic pleasure, content and structure equal to the possibility of the reader of the original. Such a balance should cover all aspects of translation.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Linguists and translators have different opinions on the issue of equivalence. According to some translators, giving the main content while strictly adhering to the norms of the language being translated is an equivalent translation, and it is emphasized that this is an acceptable situation. In general, "equivalent" is equality, firstly, when equivalence implies no similarity at all, and secondly, equivalent is substitution. For example, in Hindi, *bacacēmanakērājāhōtēha-ai* (bachche man ke raja hote heyn) "Children become kings from the heart" or it is appropriate to translate this proverb as "childhood-kingship". In this case, it is possible to achieve equivalence in translation by giving its main meaning without compromising the level of

translation. Therefore, in the process of working on a piece of the original text, several variants of translation arise. It is important that the translator can choose the best alternative. In this case, the translator selects individual elements of the text according to the level of importance, which are grammatically and semantically correct. Choosing the translation option with the least loss is the most important factor that determines the level of translation.

It is important to recognize the levels of equivalence in translation. This has been interpreted differently by linguists and linguists.

Translation, as a special type of interlingual communication, is a creative process that requires the main attention to be paid to the meaning aspect of two language systems. Because the basis of completeness of information is the spiritual harmony of the texts of different languages. One of the tasks of the goal of communication is to fully provide the aspects of the meaning alternative of any image means in translation.

The general structure and content of the text, which is the main unit of communication, is the field of experience that forms the communicative meaning of linguistic units. The semantic (spiritual) content of the text, which is a complete communicative linguistic structure, consists of denotative and significant parts. The first of these refers to the aspects of the content of the text related to the events taking place in reality, and the second is related to the verbal thinking activity of the creator of the text or speech.

We mentioned above that the content of communicative units requires the combination of all spiritual elements, the expression of a single content, the goal of communication. Accordingly, in the field of communicative semantics, we are interested not in the relations outside the sign, but in the manifestation of these relations in the speech structure through the sign.

J. Lyons, the author of the book "Semantics", which is popular among semasiologists, says that the speaker, while performing an action, purposefully chooses a linguistic expression and "expresses the reference in the content of this expression". According to him, "reference-interprets not as the result of a one-way action performed by a speaker or writer, but as a type of linguistic activity that is formed on the basis of a two-way, that is, "interpersonal action" involving the speaker and the listener".

We also like this approach, because any language activity requires a communication environment, and language communication is a manifestation of interpersonal relations, regardless of what form it takes.

In addition to describing a situation or together with it, the purpose of communication may be to express an emotion, an emotional reaction to the information provided or the situation being described. The language has special tools to express this attitude: a specific tone, signs and kh.z. We are not talking about a specific emotional component of this sign, but about special signs that provide information about the assessment of the entire situation being described. By interacting with the content of other levels, this information is often an important aspect of the communicative act.

In the works of A. Schweitzer, A. Neubert, it is explained in detail that translation is a product of interlingual communication. As a result, the long-standing debate between linguists and literary scholars has almost been put to an end.

According to A.D. Schweitzer, the most important thing in translation is the communicative equivalence of the original and translated texts based on the invariant communicative effect. Communicative equivalence is related to functional equivalence, which implies preserving the functional dominance of the original text in translation. In his theories, it

is emphasized that if communicative equivalence is applied to semantic and pragmatic levels and supplemented with functional equivalence, it is possible to talk about complete equivalence.

From the point of view that language is primarily a means of mutual communication, Sh.Sirojiddinov, based on the approaches of the communicative model of translation, explained the issue of translation equivalence in his research. His model includes the following six approaches:

1. Reflecting the statement of the objective entity expressed in the original language (denotative)
2. Revealing the attitude of the author of the original to the text being created (expressive)
3. Determining and ensuring the level of compatibility of speech signals, facial expressions, gestures and general phrases related to mutual contact (phatic)
4. Analysis of language features used in interaction (metalinguistic function)
5. Expressing commands and commands in translation (will function)
6. Full provision of artistic image tools and semantic alternative aspects in translation (poetic function)

A.D. Schweitzer describes the types of equivalence based on the results of semiotics, that is, the science that studies the sign system. Communication is carried out through these signs. According to his classification, he emphasizes that neologisms, aphorisms, folk proverbs and expressions are included in maintaining the purpose of communication. because of this, there is a risk of not being able to distinguish their original meaning.

V. N. Komissarov presents a broader model of the level of equivalence. In the last refined variant, his proposed model consists of 5 interrelated hierarchical layers:

1. The level of the purpose of communication (communication);
2. The level of describing the situation;
3. The level of the method of describing the situation;
4. Level of phrase structure;
5. Level of lexical-semantic compatibility.

V.N. According to Komissarov's theory, translation equivalence is the maximum similarity of the content of the original and translated texts. In every language, there are words with an emotional color based on the positive or negative attitude of the speaker.

Words that do not have any emotional coloring, which are found in many dictionaries, are called neutral emotional words. Based on this, lexical combinations can be divided into three types. 1) negative emotional, 2) neutral emotional, 3) positive emotional words. The emotional coloring of words is created in two different ways, by choosing the context-appropriate meaning of ambiguous words and adding emotional coloring to words. We examined this emotional coloring in our research, that is, through analogies given in the original and the translation.

In addition, expressions have a special place among the means of expressing imagery in the language, because they express negative meanings such as cursing, hatred, disgust, swearing, cursing, and positive additional meanings such as caressing, humor, encouragement. are figurative compounds. Every writer has their own style and direction of using phrases. If it is necessary to translate a work created in a certain language into another language, in particular, in the process of turning phrases, alternative options, synonyms or equivalents available in the language are used.

There are expressions whose meaning cannot be deduced directly from some of the words in its composition. At the same time, there is no contradiction between the meaning

derived from the phrase as a whole and the meanings of the words in the phrase. The words that make up the phrase do not retain their independent center of meaning. The meaning of the phrase is derived as a common denominator of the meanings inherent in the words contained in it. This general figurative meaning preserves the integrity of the phrase, does not allow it to fall apart.

The similarity of expressions in different languages is explained by the commonality of living conditions, customs and logical observations of peoples in most cases. After all, phrases, like language tools, are created on the basis of various general human opinion and life observations. Meaning and methodological task. expressions of two languages that are similar in terms of their aspects differ from each other in a number of cases. Such expressions are in the relationship of mutual equivalence. Phrases serve to preserve the purpose of communication in the text. In achieving this goal, the translator serves to convey the figurative meaning of the word given in the text to the recipient.

The interaction of the translator with the author of the original text and the receiver of the text translation changes according to the conditions of translation and the request of the receiver, the ability of the translator to understand the communicative effect, his ideas about the real or supposed receiver of the speech work, and determines the compatibility of the translation.

SUMMARY

In conclusion, it can be said that in the analysis of the above examples, we considered whether expressions and similes in Bhisham Sahni's novel "Basanti" are given their equivalent directly, that is, adequately or indirectly

The original and translation units can be equivalent at all levels or at some of them. Fully or partially equivalent units and potentially equivalent definitions objectively exist in the original language and in the translated language, but their correct evaluation, selection and application depends on the translator's knowledge, skills and creativity, his language skills. and depends on the skill of considering and comparing extralinguistic factors. When studying the translation of phrases, the translator's skill is clearly visible mainly in finding equivalent and alternative options, because the words given in simple language in Hindi are expressed by phrases in the translation. It was observed that the meaning shifts in the equivalent expressions in the original and translated texts, and when the expressions in the original are moved to the translation field, their meaning narrows and they take on a new meaning as an addition. and managed to preserve the meaning in both languages.

Adequate interpretation of phrases in translation is one of the most complex and, at the same time, very responsible issues of translation practice. Because, as artistic and descriptive means of speech, they participate in the expression of various methodological tasks more than a simple, neutral statement of thought.

From the researches of many researchers, it became known that phrases as a single lexical unit of the language can be studied grammatically, semantically, functionally, and even sociologically. In addition, many expressions have a national character, which creates difficulties for translators. Social events, moral and spiritual-cultural norms, mental states, religious imagination, national traditions and customs are reflected in the structure of each language phraseology.

From the above, it can be said that in the translation, the translator achieved translation equivalence by changing the words that correspond exactly to the content and meaning. We were sure that it could be.

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